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HOMOTYPIC CELL-CELL FUSION OF TNBC CELLS DURABLY INCREASES CELL PLOIDY AND ALTERS PHENOTYPE

Andrea L. Gardner¹, Kennedy Howland¹, Lan Zheng¹, Chisom Iloegbunam², Patrik Parker¹, Amy Brock¹

¹ The University of Texas at Austin, Austin, TX, USA

² Morehead State University, Morehead, KY, USA

Background: Understanding the mechanisms which drive intratumoral heterogeneity is especially important in triple negative breast cancer (TNBC) which does not have targeted treatment options and is characteristically heterogeneous. Fusion between cancer cells of different types or different origins is known to generate genetic heterogeneity and often leads to more pathological phenotypes. However, few studies have investigated the impact of cell-cell fusion between clonally-related cells. Without new genetic information added, do more pathological phenotypes still arise? Does the process of cell-cell fusion itself generate phenotypic heterogeneity?

Aims: This project aims to experimentally investigate the lasting impact of homotypic cell-cell fusion on TNBC cell phenotype.

Methods: HCC1806 TNBC cells were stably labeled with nuclear-localized GFP or mCherry. GFP and mCherry cells were co-cultured for 1 week, then fusion cells (double positive for GFP and mCherry) and control cells (single positive for GFP or mCherry) were isolated as single cells via FACS. Single cells were clonally expanded for more than 20 generations before experimentation, such that measured phenotypic differences between fusion and control subclones may be attributable to long lasting alterations. 9 independent fusion subclones and 9 independent control subclones were used in experiments for a total sample size of $n=18$ in all experiments. Chromosome number, growth rate, motility, chemotherapeutic response, and transcriptome were experimentally measured for each subclone.

Results: To determine if fusion subclones maintain increased ploidy or undergo ploidy reduction, cells were karyotyped using an in-house protocol at the earliest experimental timepoint and after an additional 5 weeks in culture. At least 7 metaphase spreads were counted for each subclone at each time point and the process was blinded to group identity. A near-perfect separation between groups was observed with highly poly-aneuploid karyotypes in all fusion subclones and with near-diploid or sub-diploid karyotypes in the control subclones. While there was variation in chromosome counts for each subclone, the mean and median counts for each were significantly different between fusion and control groups (mean chromosome number = 81 (3.5N) for fusion versus 39 (1.7N) for control subclones, $p=2.2e-16$) and this difference was retained in the later timepoint.

Next, we asked if fusion subclones were phenotypically different from controls. Live cell imaging revealed that growth rate and motility were significantly increased in the fusion subclones. The mean proliferation rate of control clones was 0.016 hr^{-1} , while proliferation rate of fusion clones was 0.038 hr^{-1} ($p=0.0083$). Motility was evaluated by directional migration to close a wound in a confluent cell monolayer ("scratch assay"). Fusion clones migrated $50.5 \text{ } \mu\text{m/hr}$ versus $19.6 \text{ } \mu\text{m/hr}$ for control clones ($p=0.00030$) over an 8 hour period. We then asked if fusion subclones differ from control clones in response to chemotherapeutics. Using endpoint viability assays, the high ploidy fusion subclones were found to be surprisingly more sensitive to mitotic inhibitors paclitaxel ($p=0.00034$) and vincristine ($p=0.038$), but highly resistant to the platinum-based agent cisplatin ($p=3.5e-6$). To provide more insight on the mechanisms which may be driving these phenotypic differences, we performed RNA-seq on each fusion and control subclone and used differential expression analysis to reveal key genes and pathways altered in fusion subclones.

Conclusion: HCC1806 subclones generated from homotypic cell-cell fusion have durably increased ploidy, are highly motile and more proliferative, have altered responses to standard chemotherapeutics, and have unique gene expression signatures. We conclude that homotypic cell-cell fusion has lasting impacts on cell phenotype and response to therapy and now seek to identify the factors driving cell-cell fusion in cancer and quantify the extent of fusion in patient samples in order to select the most effective treatment strategies.